

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– No

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: حكم الإمامة القائم على مبدأ الشورى

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:
– Yes

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:
– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:
– Yes

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):
– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):
– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:
– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
– No

- ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - No
- ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - No
- ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - No
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
 - No
- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - No

Notes: القائد غير معصوم من الخطأ

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

- ↳ Are they written:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they oral:
 - No
- ↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
 - Yes
- ↳ Revealed by a high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:
 - Yes

- ↳ Inspired by high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:
 - No
- ↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:
 - No
- ↳ Originated from non-divine human being:
 - No

- ↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
 - No
- ↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:
 - Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:
– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:
– Yes

↳ Temples:
– Yes

Notes: أنماط معمارية لمساجد كثيرة في العهد الرستمي

↳ Altars:
– No

↳ Devotional markers:
– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– Yes [specify]: العمارة الأثرية الاباضية

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
– On persons
– At home
– Only religious public space
– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: الهلال، النجمة الخماسية، اليد...

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: أيقونات في شكل خواتم وسلاسل عنق وصور في البيوت وعلى الأبواب

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: المساجد

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: الحج الأكبر إلى مكة

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: هناك وصف للجنة وجنهم ولكن مكان الحياة الآخرة بالضبط غير محدد تدقيقا مع الإشارة إلى الأدنى من الأرض بين مكة والقدس

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable items:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

- ↳ Other formal burial type:
–Yes [specify]: الدفن في المقابر العامة والعائلية

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:
– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: **فَلَهُ** **هُوَ** **لِلَّهِ** **أَخَذَ** **۱۰** **لِلَّهِ** **لِصَّمَدٍ** **۲۰** **لَمْ** **يَلِدْ** **وَلَمْ** **يُولَدْ** **۳۰** **وَلَمْ** **يَكُنْ** **لَهُ** **كُفُوًا** **۴۰**
[الإخلاص ٤-١] يعني: هو الواحد الأحد، الذي لا نظير له ولا وزير، ولا نديد ولا شبيه ولا عدل، ولا يطلق هذا اللفظ على أحد في الإنبات إلا على الله عز وجل؛ لأنه الكامل في جميع صفاته وأفعاله.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: رب السموات والأرض

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: مالك الملك

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: الدين

Notes: الولاء عبر الدين والعبادة لله وحده لا شريك له

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: لا إله وحده له الملك وله الحمد وهو على كل شيء قدير

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: يوجد تسعة وتسعون اسما وصفة للإله وهي مذكورة في القرآن الكريم

Notes: ...،الرحمان، الرحيم، الباسط، الصمد، الرب، الكامل، الناصح، الغفور، الكبير، القدوس، المهيمن

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No
Notes: يعلم كل شيء

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: يعلم ما في السموات والأرض

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: يعلم السر وما يخفى

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: يعلم النفس والهوى والنوايا

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: يعلم ما نعلم وما لا نعلم

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: المكافئة بالحسنات والجنة والصحة والعافية وطول العمر

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes:...السينات وجهنم والمرض والهم والغم وسوء الطالع

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: غفور رحيم
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: شديد العقاب
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
 - Notes: يمتلك كل شيء
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
 - Notes: لا إله إلا هو ولا يعبد إلا هو
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: الأسماء 99 كلها ميزات وأوصاف لله سبحانه وتعالى
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - Notes: "عبر الدعاء والاجابة" أدعوني استجب لكم
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: التواصل سرميدي مع الأحياء والأموات
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - Notes: يمكن رؤيتهم من طرف الأنبياء الدينون
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - Notes: تأثير الجن في الانسان
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: مس الجن للأنس
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: الجن مخلوق من نار وفيه المسلم وفيه الكافر
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: القرآن هو علم الله الأبدى الذي علم الانسان

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: أعراف مرتبطة بالعرق وأخرى بالدين والمذهب

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: المذهب الديني الاباضي

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):
– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes

- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– No
Notes: في حدود الدين والطاعة والاحترام
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
Notes: الذي لا يتعارض والدين
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes

- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: كل الفضائل السابقة

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: الزواج الشرعي مقبول

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: صيام شهر رمضان فرض للجميع وفيه صيام النوافل

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: الخمر ولم الخنزير والمؤودة وما أهل به لغير الله والميتة والدم كلها محرمة على المسلمين

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: الصلاة والعبادة، الصدقات، الدعوة لله وللإسلام...

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: مبادئ وأخلاق الإسلام

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 3

Notes: مثلا بين الصلوات الجماعية بين 2 و3 ساعات في المتوسط

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: الامام والفقهاء مثلا يحتاج إلى فحوصات فقهية

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– I don't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: الركوع مثلا والسجود والاصطفاف وتوحيد الصفوف

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– I don't know

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– I don't know

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– No

↳ Ornaments:

– I don't know

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– I don't know

- ↳ Other:
 - I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

- Yes

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
 - Yes
 - Notes: الاخوة، ابن العم، محمد

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
 - Yes

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
 - No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

- Yes

Notes: بيت مال المسلمين

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

- Yes

Notes: التكافل الاجتماعي، الزكاة، الصدقات

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

- No

Notes: بر الوالدين من شأن الأبناء في الاسلام

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: بيت المال

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):
– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:
– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:
– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:
– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:
– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:
– Gathering
– Hunting (including marine animals)
– Fishing
– Pastoralism
– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
– Other [specify in comments]

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: n.d., الدولة الرسمية، يوركية، محمد. الجزائر الاجتماعية في عهد الدولة الرسمية. الجزائر: دار الكفاية.

Reference: الدولة الرسمية، الحريري، محمد عيسى. الدولة الرسمية بالمغرب الاسلامي. الكويت: دار القلم للنشر والتوزيع، 1987.

Reference: الدولة الرسمية، محمد زينهم ، محمد عزب. قيام وتطور الدولة الرسمية في تاريخ المغرب. القاهرة: دار العالم العربي، 2013.

Reference: الدولة الرسمية، حياوي، فراس سليم. "، جوانب من الصلات الخارجية للدولة الرسمية، جامعة بابل، 2007". العراق: <https://www.researchgate.net/>, 2007.

Reference: الدولة الرسمية، جودت، عبد الكريم. العلاقات الخارجية الرسمية. الجزائر: المؤسسة الوطنية للكتاب، 1984.

Reference: "الدولة الرسمية، السرجاني، راعب". <http://97.105.52.213/ar/artical/19988>, 2016.

Reference: "محاضرة الدولة الرسمية في المغرب الأوسط - الجزائر (160-296هـ/777-1600م)". <https://elearn.univ-oran1.dz/course/view.php?id=4199>, 2023. م909م، وهران

Reference: الدولة الرسمية، الدرجيني، الشيخ ابن العباس أحمد بن سعيد . . كتاب طبقات المشايخ بالمغرب. قسنطينة، الجزائر: AD، مطبعة البعث، 670

Reference: AD، الدولة الرسمية، ابن الصغير. أخبار الأئمة الرسميين. بيروت: دار الغرب الاسلامي، 300

Reference: "عوامل ضعف وسقوط دولة بني رستم في المغرب الأوسط سنة ٦٩٢هـ/ 1300م". [السعودية: مجلة "وقائع تاريخية" العدد \(53\)، ٦٠٦٠. يوليو](https://www.saudia.net/) (مركز البحوث والدراسات التاريخية الجزء الأول، 2021

Reference: "الحركة الفكرية بالدولة الرسمية وإسهام المرأة الإباضية فيها". وهران، الجزائر: مجلة Volume 1, Numéro 1, Pages 63-75 2011-04-16, 2011. عصور الجديدة، جامعة وهران

Reference: "الدولة الرسمية دولة إسلامية ظلما التاريخ". سلطنة عمان: <https://www.istiqama.net/history/aldawlah-arustomyiah.htm>, n.d.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: محمد عيسى الحريري، الدولة الرسمية بالمغرب الاسلامي، دار القلم للنشر والتوزيع، الكويت، الطبعة: 1987، الثالثة، Source 2: 1984، الجزائر، المؤسسة الوطنية للكتاب، الجزائر، Source 3: محمد زينهم محمد عزب، قيام وتطور الدولة الرسمية في المغرب، دار العالم العربي، القاهرة، طبعة أولى، 2013، Source 4: بحاز، إبراهيم بكير. الدولة الرسمية: دراسة في الأوضاع الاقتصادية والحياة الفكرية. القرارة، الجزائر: نشر جمعية التراث، 1993.